

Fermentation of Rice Straw by *Bacillus Acetoethylicus*.

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That pentoses could be fermented by some bacteria has long been known to bacteriologists. With *Bac. ethaceticus* Frankland (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 60, 492, 737) obtained 11.2-12.3 per cent. of alcohol from arabinose. Tollens (*J. Inst. Brewing*, 1898, 4, 488) experimented upon an organism which produced ethyl alcohol from xylose.

Northrop, Ashe and Senior (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, 39, 1) reported the isolation of a bacterium capable of fermenting pentoses and hexoses to acetone and ethyl alcohol. They named the organism *Bacillus acetoethylicus*. They obtained 18 to 20 per cent. alcohol with 4 to 5 per cent. of acetone calculating on the quantities of sugar fermented. Attempts to utilise *Bac. acetoethylicus* to produce alcohol and acetone from pentoses were made the subjects of study by Northrop and his collaborators (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1919, 11, 72f), Peterson, Fred and Verhulst (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 757) and Fred, Peterson and Anderson (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 126). The general conclusion reached by the different authors is that the fermentation of pentoses by *Bac. acetoethylicus* is normally slow taking from eight to ten days for completion. Northrop, Ashe and Morgan claimed an increase in the rate of fermentation by addition of oak or beech shavings to the fermenting mixture. Peterson, Fred and Verhulst (*loc. cit.*) stated that addition of peptone and disodium phosphate and the maintenance of the reaction of the fermenting liquid between p_H 6 and 9 by suitable addition of calcium carbonate hastened the fermentation.

In addition to fermenting pentoses and hexoses to ethyl alcohol and acetone, the organism also converts a part of the sugar supplied into formic and acetic acids. Thus Fred, Peterson and Anderson obtained from hydrolysed oat hulls 26.9 per cent. of alcohol, 12.7 per cent. of acetone and 6.71 per cent. of volatile fatty acids. Donker ("Bijdrage tot de Kennis, der Boterzuur-Butylalcohol en acetonegisting," Publ. W. D. Meinema, Delft, 1926) states that from hexoses he obtained about 2.6 per cent. of formic acid and 5.2 per

cent. of acetic acid. Thaysen and Galloway (*Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 1928, 15, 392) obtained from hydrolysed wheat straw 1.77 per cent. of acetic acid and 12.6 per cent. of formic acid. They also found that the concentration of acetone was higher when the fermenting medium contained hexoses than when only pentoses were present. According to them the yields of acetone and alcohol were always variable. Neither increase in the internal surface nor the addition of peptone and dipotassium phosphate improved the rate of conversion to any appreciable extent.

Thaysen ("Fuel for Motor Transport," Fourth Memorandum, published by His Majesty's Stationery Office, 1927) made an extensive study of the possibility of converting cellulosic waste materials into the fermentable sugars. He concluded that the best results were obtained when the grasses and straw were steeped in two per cent. sulphuric acid for four hours followed by steaming for six hours at ordinary pressure. Unpublished work done in this laboratory showed that the time of steeping did not matter so long as acid was allowed to be uniformly soaked up by the straw, for which purpose one hour was found to be sufficient.

It was found that Thaysen's figures for pentoses obtained from rice straw by his process could not be confirmed. With one hour's steeping in two per cent. sulphuric acid followed by six hour's steaming at atmospheric pressure only six to seven per cent. of reducing sugars were obtained. Similar experiments with four per cent. and six per cent. acids almost doubled and trebled the yields of reducing sugars. The straw used for this purpose was local rice straw and not the Burma variety which was used by Thaysen.

All the previous workers found that *Bac. acetothylicus* would ferment only small concentrations of pentoses. The bacillus would not ferment 5 per cent. sugar solution, but gave satisfactory results when the concentrations ranged between 2 and 3 per cent. It was with a view to train the bacillus to ferment concentrations of pentoses higher than these that the present piece of work was undertaken.

The observation of the previous workers that the best results were obtained by keeping the concentration of pentoses near about three per cent. was confirmed.

It was observed that increasing the concentrations of sugars above three per cent. generally decreased the yields of alcohol and acetone till at 7 per cent. the yields were reduced to quantities of little practical use. Changing the nutrient mixtures from ammonium

phosphate and peptone to combinations of ammonium nitrate, disodium hydrogen phosphate and yeast water did not materially improve the yields.

When carrying out subcultures to train the organism to higher concentration of pentoses, it was observed that the presence of small quantities of hexoses, such as glucose, always facilitated the growth of the organism and the fermentation of pentoses. The bacillus was trained to ferment 7 per cent. pentoses. Starting from a concentration of three per cent. first it was acclimatised to five per cent. and then to seven per cent. pentose concentration. In this process diminishing quantities of added hexoses were used with increasing concentration of pentoses until an abundant growth of the organism and vigorous fermentation were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydrolysis of Straw by dilute Sulphuric Acid.—A weighed quantity of chopped straw (100 g.) was packed into a lead pot and steeped for one hour in a definite volume of sulphuric acid of known strength. After squeezing out the superfluous sulphuric acid, the residue was steamed for six hours at atmospheric pressure. Reducing sugars were washed and pressed out from the digested straw and after neutralising with calcium carbonate were estimated as usual. Yields of reducing sugars are presented in Table I.

TABLE I.

Per cent. acid.	2	4	6
Per cent. reducing sugars as hexoses.	6.9-9.5	11.6	18.9

To obtain a good yield of reducing sugars a much higher percentage of acid than the one recommended by Thaysen has to be used. About 400 c. c. of dilute acid were generally required for hydrolysing 100 g. of straw.

Fermentation of the Hydrolysed Straw by Bacillus Acetoethylicus.
—(a) Fermentations were carried out at 37° for 8—10 days in small flasks containing measured quantities of the concentrated hydrolysate together with ammonium phosphate and either peptone or yeast water. It was found that a very small concentration of peptone favoured good growth and fermentation, the optimum being about 0.05% (Table II).

Figures indicate percentage of reducing sugars in the media. The bacillus was trained to ferment 7% pentose medium in the following steps :

Medium.	Pentose (straw extract).	Glucose added.	Transfers.
1	4.5%	0.5%	2
2	5.0	2.0	2
3	5.5	1.5	2
4	6.0	1.0	2
5	6.5	0.5	1
6	7.0	0.0	—

(c) The yield of acetone-alcohol mixtures varied considerably, no direct cause being found for this variation. The best results obtained utilising 4% reducing sugar solutions are given below in Table III.

Reducing sugar in all flasks before fermentation was 4.1 g. per 100 c. c. of reaction mixture. Flasks were incubated at 37° for seven days.

TABLE III.

Flask no.	Sugar fermented.	Acetone—alcohol mixture.
16	3.24 g.	0.8089 g.
18	3.24	0.7166
19	3.50	0.8728
23	3.36	0.8386
27	3.20	0.7424

(d) Some fermentation results with media containing 7% reducing sugars.

TABLE IV.

Flask no.	Total sugar before fermenta- tion.	Total sugar after fermentation.	Acetone— alcohol.	Total acid : equivalent to c.c. of N/10-alkali.
71	3.4 g.	0.940 g.	0.404 g.	—
72	3.4	0.550	0.446	43.0
76	3.4	0.460	0.350	49.8
78	3.5	0.680	0.288	37.2
81	3.5	0.487	0.484	47.0

The results given above represent the best of the lot. The range of loss of sugars by fermentation lay between 75 and 87%. The corresponding production of acetone and alcohol mixture was considerably less than that from 4% sugar media. In other cases where about the same percentage of sugars were lost, the power mixture was still less than what the figures represent in Table IV

Summary.

(1) It has not been found practicable to train *Bac. acetabutylicus* to ferment high concentrations of pentoses, e.g., 7 per cent. The yields of acetone—alcohol mixtures obtained from fermenting 7 per cent. pentoses (present in the straw hydrolysate) were too low to be of any practical importance from the viewpoint of commercial application.

(2) In training the bacillus for the above purpose the presence of hexoses in small quantities were found to be necessary at each step in the increase in pentose concentration.

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